

CURRENT STATE OF THE PERSONNEL TRAINING SYSTEM FOR THE PUBLIC SECURITY SERVICE OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

M.D.Jakhongirov

Employee of the Department of Internal Affairs
of Samarkand region

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Abstract: This article comprehensively analyzes the current state of the personnel training system for the public security service of internal affairs bodies. The study examines current educational processes, curricula, and modern pedagogical approaches in training personnel serving in the field of public safety. Additionally, existing problems in the personnel training system, shortcomings in developing practical skills, as well as scientifically substantiated proposals and recommendations aimed at addressing these issues are presented. The article also analyzes reforms in the field, the regulatory framework, and opportunities for implementing international experience. The research results will contribute to improving the system of training highly qualified, professionally and spiritually developed personnel for the public security service of internal affairs bodies.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, public security service, personnel training system, professional training, educational process, practical skills, reforms, modern pedagogical approaches, law enforcement agencies.

The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026, adopted at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, states that a number of reforms have been implemented in the area of "...ensuring human rights, strengthening the accountability and transparency of government bodies..."[1]. Based on these reforms, internal affairs bodies will be transformed into a socially oriented professional structure that provides timely and high-quality assistance to the population, with each of its employees considering "Serving the interests of the people" as their official duty.

In our country, the processes of protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensuring the security of individuals, society, and the state, as well as preventing and combating offenses are becoming increasingly complex and urgent. The effective implementation of these tasks is directly related to the activities of internal affairs bodies in personnel management.

The functions of internal affairs bodies in organizing work with personnel are assigned to the personnel service and its structural subdivisions on the basis of current legislation. Personnel units of internal affairs bodies are one of the independent structural subdivisions of the internal affairs bodies, the main activity of which is related to the admission of citizens to the service of internal affairs bodies, appointment to positions, promotion and transfer to other positions, as well as ensuring professional training, providing legal and social assistance to employees and their families, observing official discipline and legislation, and implementing state policy in the field of organizational and staffing work.

Based on these reforms, a Program of Comprehensive Measures for the Fundamental Reform of the Internal Affairs Bodies System was approved. Clause 3 of the Program provides for issues of strengthening personnel potential through the introduction of advanced

mechanisms for training, selection, and placement of personnel, improving their qualifications and moral and ethical qualities.

The reforms being carried out in the system, firstly, ensure the effective fulfillment of the main tasks assigned to the internal affairs bodies and the new tasks imposed on them based on modern requirements; secondly, international law requires officials of law enforcement agencies, as well as civil servants, in particular, employees of internal affairs bodies, based on the requirements of national legislation, to be professional specialists with high moral, ethical, and professional qualities.

Personnel work in the system of internal affairs bodies is a complex and multifaceted process, and the main tasks of its organization are:

1) organization of the selection, study and placement of employees of internal affairs bodies, formation of a reserve of managerial personnel and work with them;

2) analysis and assessment of the state of personnel work, determination of priority areas for its further improvement and strengthening of the personnel potential of internal affairs bodies;

3) timely detection, suppression, and prevention of instances of abuse of office, corruption, and other unlawful acts by employees;

4) organization of professional, physical, and combat training of personnel;

5) organization of the process of training, retraining and advanced training of employees;

6) ensuring the training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel in educational institutions of the internal affairs bodies;

7) organization of moral and educational work with employees, encouragement and disciplinary action;

8) taking measures to suppress instances of interference in the lawful activities of employees;

9) organization of healthcare for employees, payment of wages, provision of housing, compensation for damage caused to the property of internal affairs officers or their close relatives in connection with the performance of official duties, state pension provision, state insurance, as well as social assistance to employees and their families in accordance with the law;

10) ensuring the combat and mobilization training of personnel.

As is known, the selection of candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies consists of a set of interconnected actions that form the content of the following stages and have a defined sequence:

1) determination of requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates;

2) study and assessment of the abilities and personal qualities of specific candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies;

3) comparison of the abilities and personal qualities of specific candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies with the requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates;

4) comparison of candidates based on their abilities and personal qualities;

5) selection of the most suitable candidates for internal affairs bodies in terms of requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates.

One of the most important measures for ensuring public safety is the provision of personnel with knowledge of modern science and technology for the functioning of this sphere based on specific mechanisms.

The reforms being implemented in this direction based on the relevant resolutions of the President of our country include, firstly, organizing a system for training highly qualified specialists in the field of ensuring public safety based on advanced international standards; secondly, increasing the personnel potential of departments in this field based on modern requirements[2]; thirdly, ensuring career growth of employees based on their qualifications; fourthly, further enhancing the intellectual and professional potential of managerial personnel in the effective management of forces and resources[3].

As a result of the reforms being carried out to improve the system of training personnel for public safety activities, firstly, as a result of a radical reform of the educational process of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the introduction of a two-stage system of higher education (bachelor's and master's degrees) and mechanisms for targeted training of personnel in the management structure, further increasing the intellectual and professional potential of managerial personnel in the effective management of forces and resources to ensure public safety; secondly, the introduction of a continuous training and career system, including an order of the educational process inextricably linked with the rules of service, ensuring career growth of employees depending on their qualifications in the public safety system; thirdly, the introduction of a system of targeted training of qualified personnel in the field of public safety provides an opportunity to train, retrain, and improve the qualifications of officer specialists in the areas of maintaining public order, road safety, and the implementation of the requirements of the passport system, which are the main units of the sphere.

The significance of the reforms in this area lies in the fact that, based on modern requirements, the Public Security University of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established to enhance the personnel potential of law enforcement agencies and the Armed Forces.

The university has been designated as a basic higher military educational and research institution for the targeted training of qualified personnel. The university, unique in world practice and for the first time in the country's history, provided young people with the opportunity to study at a higher military educational institution on a civilian basis, with girls admitted to study in the military field[5].

In general, it can be said that as a result of the reforms being carried out in the internal affairs bodies, a system of state administration in the sphere of internal affairs is being created, capable of timely identification and effective solution of problems of socio-political and socio-economic development, meeting global trends in innovative development.

The system of internal affairs bodies is being fundamentally reviewed on the basis of:

- 1) the system is being optimized and decentralized by eliminating redundant and non-specific tasks, functions, and powers, eliminating duplication and parallelism;
- 2) measures are being taken to eliminate bureaucracy in the system, and the role of management decision-making in ensuring the effectiveness and transparency of activities is being increased;
- 3) a system of strategic planning, innovative ideas, developments, and technologies is being introduced;

4) effective forms of public and parliamentary control are being introduced, primarily aimed at preventing manifestations of corruption.

In order to create effective mechanisms for ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens, further increasing their well-being and satisfaction with the activities of internal affairs bodies, the following are being implemented:

1) administrative procedures aimed at the precise regulation of the legal relations of internal affairs bodies with individuals and legal entities are being improved;

2) the procedure for appealing decisions and actions of internal affairs bodies is being improved;

3) The effectiveness of the provision of public services in the system of internal affairs bodies is increasing through the improvement of the "E-Government" system.

The fundamental reforms being implemented in the system of internal affairs bodies, in particular, in the field of personnel work, serve to ensure that each employee of the internal affairs bodies, in fulfilling the tasks assigned to them, has a high level of moral and professional training to fully implement the ideas "Not the people should serve state bodies, but state bodies should serve the people," "Justice is the rule of law."

Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. Significant work has been carried out, in particular, on the development and strengthening of the lower level of internal affairs bodies, organized to maintain public order in mahallas, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime.

In Uzbekistan, civil society institutions play an invaluable role in further strengthening the guarantees of the human being, their life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights, recognized as the highest value, and in realizing their aspirations.

The inextricable link between the concepts of independence, the Constitution, civil society, and democracy is of great importance. Indeed, it is impossible to imagine an independent country without a democratic state governed by the rule of law and strong civil society institutions. Therefore, from the first days of independence, the path of democratic renewal and building a free civil society was chosen in our country. Consequently, everyone traverses this path in their own unique way. Uzbekistan, based on the fundamental principles of democracy and strictly adhering to them, is currently conducting its actions in accordance with the thinking and millennia-old way of life of our people.

Legality and legal order in society are established by the lawful actions of citizens, the observance of laws by all state bodies and public associations, and their proper use. Establishing stability, peace, and tranquility in society, ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms, is an important condition for achieving the goals of the large-scale reforms being carried out for the further socio-economic development of the country, improving the well-being of the population, and building a legal democratic state.

An integrated legal system has been created in the republic for the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the protection of public order, ensuring the security of the individual, society, and the state, and the prevention and prophylaxis of offenses, in which internal affairs bodies play an important role.

As mentioned above, internal affairs bodies fulfill the tasks of strengthening legality and law and order, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, and combating crime. Carry out inquiries and preliminary investigations in cases within their competence, ensure

peace and the security of humanity. The importance of the implementation of the tasks of internal affairs bodies increases even more in the context of the formation of a legal state and the building of civil society.

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